

INTRODUCTION

The geographical diversity of the origin of both editorial staff and authors is one of the key criteria in the selection of journals for internationally respected databases (Scopus, Web of Science, etc.). Normally, well-established world-class journals have their own readers, regular authors, and also engage new ones due to their strong performance (Hirsch index, quartile, etc.).

Many new periodicals aiming at international recognition face the problem of finding overseas editors and authors of articles. It is more difficult for periodicals that are not included in authoritative databases to compete in inviting new authors with more reputable ones.

As a result of journal evaluations, members of the Scopus Content Selection & Advisory Board state that journals need to significantly expand their international reach in terms of authorship and academic influence. They recommend publishing more articles in English and looking for authors that are more influential from other countries. The recommendations are certainly valuable but such questions arise as how to bring foreign authors?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In preparing the article, such queries through the Google search engine were used as "How does a journal attract authors?" in both English and Russian.

In the review of sources, contemporary foreign periodicals were used, such as Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, Journal of Strategic Marketing, Quantitative Marketing and Economics, Service Business, Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian, etc.

When writing the article, the author relied on many years of experience in promoting the Economic Consultant journal (formerly the State Councillor).

RESULTS

General principles and practical recommendations for soliciting new customers for a purchase or service are presented quite well in scientific periodicals.

David J. Reibstein rightly notes that it is important to not only attract new customers but also retain them, and this requires feedback on the survey results, analysis of their behaviour on the site, etc. [1].

Rizal Ahmad and Francis Buttle believe that customer retention is a potentially effective marketing management strategy and should be part of strategic marketing planning [2].

Neda Mizani et al. suggest drawing and retaining customers with the rough set theory [3].

According to Seung Hwan (Shawn) Lee and Scott Fay, the prices of goods and services for old customers should tend to decrease compared to those for new ones [4].

Leigh McAlister and Shameek Sinha believe that most client portfolio management models are "short-term" meaning they are designed to increase profits from existing customers in the next period and only consider existing customers. The authors propose a client portfolio management model designed to maintain a company's long-term viability. This long-term perspective requires the company to take into account the balance in its customer structure [5].

In analysing banking services, Kreituss et al. identified five factors that should be taken into account in working out a strategic marketing activity plan, such as service quality; convenient remote banking services (online banking, telephone banking, mobile banking); the bank reputation; the bank's financial stability; and, finally, the bank's service charges [6].

Sang M. Lee and DonHee Lee write that customer communications often occur without any personal contact with employees [7], as is virtually the case in the publishing industry now.

Fangfang Li et al. propose to attract customers through social networks while taking into account their behaviour classification: consumption (for example, reading messages), involvement (for example, product evaluation), and creation (for example, publishing some company-related content) [8].

Very few scientific articles were found to engage and retain new authors, i.e. customers, in the publication of articles in the journal.

Basically, those are lots of recommendations on the publishers' and professional communities' websites. For example, on the Jisc website, when asked "How to get authors to publish in your new university press", recommendations are given: provide an exceptional experience; build a good reputation; show that you take good care of the authors; make sure you post high-quality works. The possibility of assessing the quality of articles by the scientific community implies open access [9].

It is worth singling out the work of Bo-Christer Bjurk and Anssi Uurni who developed and tested a comparative journal analysis method making it possible for authors to obtain the most complete information about them. The authors identified such parameters as readership; scientific prestige; time from submission to publication; percentage of acceptance; services provided by the journal during the peer review and publication [10].

As noted earlier, there are a lot of recommendations for promoting a journal in order to engage potential authors who would like to submit their articles to the journal. However, the authors' hands-on experience suggests that attracting foreign authors is a rather challenging task. This is due to the fact that the availability of an English-language version of the journal and open access do not yet guarantee a response from them (i.e. foreign authors) [11].

Tarkhanov considered special tools and technologies used by popular Internet media:

- SEO optimisation of the journal's website for its good indexing in search engines (Google, Yandex, etc.);
- Contextual advertising tools (Yandex Direct and Google AdWords services, etc.);
- Registration in dedicated catalogues and well-known scientometric databases (RSCI, Google Scholar, Academia.edu, etc.);

- Creation of a multilingual, or at least a bilingual version of the journal; availability of a mobile version of the publication; RSS news feeds arrangements, etc.

The Scholastica journal platform website describes "3 steps to attract more high-quality materials to your journal"^{*}. Let us study those tips.

The first tip is to invite leading scientists to your editorial board. Indeed, in addition to building a reputation, each invited editor has the potential to help introduce the journal to a wider audience through their academic networks.

The second step is to invite renowned scientists to act as guest editors for special issues on specific topics of interest in the field. It is likely that finding conferences, at which scholars have delivered a series of related and relevant papers, published abstracts, is an effective aid in inviting those scholars to submit their work for a special issue.

The third rule is to promote a journal as a matter of priority and involve leading scientists. Certainly, the editorial board should actively support conversations about the journal with fellow scientists in person and via the Internet. What is meant is placing calls for the publication of articles and new articles on social networks (Twitter, Facebook, etc.); creating a blog for publishing the journal announcements and materials about authors (authors to participate in blogs can be invited).

The Academic Journal Management Best Practices guide provides a few more recommendations:

- direct appeal to renowned scientists in a specific scientific field;
- publishing editorials, comments, and other short materials;
- leave a good impression of the journal after contacting the authors by e-mail, telephone; inform authors about the progress of peer review, etc. [12].

Thus, in attracting high-quality materials, an integrated approach to the development of a publication is required in such aspects as the site of the journal as its "face"; the content; communication with authors; referring to external resources.

The above tips and recommendations often advocate for the invitation of renowned scientists. In the case of foreign researchers, it probably means an invitation either via e-mail or professional social networks (ResearchGate, Google Scholar, Academia.edu, etc.).

The authors' experience suggests that even a targeted e-mail distribution (inviting specific authors) as a tool for finding authors and increasing publication activity is poorly effective, since authors are mainly interested in respected journals indexed in international scientometric databases. According to Morgunova, "many experienced authors immediately delete such letters; so, it is virtually impossible to attract them in this way. Whatever is written in a letter, it is unlikely to be read" [13].

It should also be noted that spam mailing of newsletters with an invitation to publish articles as a method of attracting new authors is a sign of an incorrect editorial policy: "The publisher, editorial staff or their partners arrange for duplicate mailings and online advertising (spam) with a proposal for quick publication in the journals RSCI, Higher Attestation Commission of the Russian Federation, etc., i.e. in order to involve authors in a

^{*} <https://blog.scholasticahq.com/post/3-steps-to-attract-more-quality-submissions-to-your-scholarly-journal/>

journal. At the same time, authors often receive invitations to publish in a journal on topics that are far from their scientific interests".

DISCUSSION

The authors agree with Tarkhanov's opinion that an online journal should have tools to attract and retain a user group. A contemporary scientific online journal is a set of Internet services integrated for communicating, promoting one's ideas, posting media materials that have not been published, and testing new approaches to handling scientific knowledge and content [14].

As Kirillova rightly notes: "not a single scientific work can be started without a preliminary study and analysis of research carried out earlier on the chosen topic or presently being in progress. The results of such an analysis of publications on the topic of research are reflected both directly in research articles and are published in the form of regular independent reviews" [15].

In connection with the above, it is important to reconsider the duties of the editorial board members, as directly authors of a new periodical, who could, for example, on the instructions of the editor-in-chief write up-to-date reviews in the related areas, headings of the journal.

It can be helpful if the published articles cover a wider range of research topics and issues that may directly affect an international audience.

Published articles can be sent directly to foreign authors referred to by authors who are members of the editorial board. Alternatively, this can induce foreign authors to a scientific dialogue; and, possibly, to publish articles in a fresh journal.

CONCLUSION

Improving the quality of a scientific journal can be associated with improving the site; the use of tools to reduce the waiting time for the release of an article; ordering articles from sound scholars; engagement in arranging for related conferences and invitation to the publication of the authors of the best reports.

It seems that this topic will be useful for not only fresh journals but also long-standing publications, which should also constantly make efforts to attract high-quality articles.

REFERENCES

1. Reibstein, D. J. (2021). What attracts customers to online stores, and what keeps them coming back?. *J. of the Acad. Mark. Sci.*, 30, 465. DOI: 10.1177/009207002236918

* <https://biblio.dissernet.org/prizn>

2. Ahmad, R., & Buttle, F. (2001). Customer retention: a potentially potent marketing management strategy. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 9 (1), 29–45, DOI: 10.1080/713775729
3. Mizani, N., Sheikh, R., Gholami, A. et al. (2018). Attracting and Retaining Customers by Axiomatic Design and Incomplete Rough-Set Theory. *Int. J. Appl. Comput. Math*, 75 (4). DOI: 10.1007/s40819-018-0507-9
4. Lee, S.H., & Fay, S. (2017). Why offer lower prices to past customers? Inducing favorable social price comparisons to enhance customer retention. *Quant Mark Econ*, 15, 123–163. DOI: 10.1007/s11129-017-9181-1
5. McAlister, L., & Sinha, S. (2021). A customer portfolio management model that relates company's marketing to its long-term survival. *J. of the Acad. Mark. Sci.*, 49, 584–600. DOI: 10.1007/s11747-020-00765-9
6. Kreituss, I., Vasiljeva, T., & Rokjane, B. (2021) Factors Important for Banks in Attracting and Retaining Customers. In: *Kabashkin I., Yatskiv I., Prentkovskis O. (eds) Reliability and Statistics in Transportation and Communication. RelStat 2020. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, 195*. Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-68476-1_64
7. Lee, S.M., & Lee, D. (2020). “Untact”: a new customer service strategy in the digital age. *Serv Bus*, 14, 1–22. DOI: 10.1007/s11628-019-00408-2
8. Li, F., Larimo, J. & Leonidou, L.C. (2021). Social media marketing strategy: definition, conceptualization, taxonomy, validation, and future agenda. *J. of the Acad. Mark. Sci.* 49, 51–70. DOI: 10.1007/s11747-020-00733-3
9. Coonin, B. & Younce, L. M. (2010). Publishing in Open Access Education Journals: The Authors' Perspectives. *Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian*, 29 (2), 118–132. DOI: 10.1080/01639261003742181
10. Bjork B.-C. (2009). A Method for Comparing Scholarly Journals as Service Providers to Authors. *Serials Review*, 35 (2), 62–69. DOI: 10.1080/00987913.2009.10765213
11. Tretyakova, O.V. (2015). Promotion of a Scientific Journal in the International Information Space: Problems and Solutions. *Economic and Social Changes: Facts, Trends, Forecast*, 3(39). Retrieved September 7, 2021, from <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/prodvizhenie-nauchnogo-zhurnala-v-mezhdunarodnom-informatsionnom-prostranstve-problemy-i-resheniya>
12. Scholastica. (2020). *Academic Journal Management Best Practices: Tales from the Trenches*. Scholastica.
13. Morgunova, G. V. (2019). What guides an author when choosing a journal to publish an article. In *Management and Development Strategy and Tactics: Materials of the 8th International Research-to-Practice Conference, Moscow, 23–26 April 2019* (pp. 78–84). Yekaterinburg: Ural Publishing House. DOI: 10.24069/konf-23-26-04-2019.12.
14. Tarkhanov, I. A. (2017). Promotion of a journal as an online media. In *Global Practice in the Preparation and Promotion of Publications: Proceedings of the 6th International Research-to-Practice Conference, Moscow, 18–21 April 2017* (pp. 128–136). Moscow.

DOI: 10.24069/2017.978-5-7996-2227-5.22

15. Kirillova, O. V. (Ed.). Guidelines for the Preparation of Scientific Articles in Journals Indexed in International Scientometric Databases. Moscow: Association of Science Editors and Publishers.
16. Mabe, M., & Mulligan, A. (2011). What journal authors want: ten years of results from Elsevier's author feedback programme. *New Review of Information Networking*, 16 (1), 71–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614576.2011.574495>
17. Shin, E. J. (2017). Can the growth of mega-journals affect authors' choice of journal? *Serials Review*, 43 (2), 137–146. DOI: 10.1080/00987913.2017.1313092
18. Yuret, T. (2016). Is it easier to publish in journals that have low impact factors? *Applied Economics Letters*, 23 (11), 801–803. DOI: 10.1080/13504851.2015.1109034

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Roman I. Ostapenko (Russia, Voronezh) – PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Director. Scientific and Educational Initiative LLC. E-mail: ramiro@list.ru. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3012-3971. ResearcherID: C-3015-2014. Scopus Author ID: 57205331507

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2021/11/28/ostapenko-4/>

Received: Apr 14, 2021 | **Accepted:** Sep 11, 2021 | **Published:** Dec 1, 2021

Editor: Norlaile S. Hudin, PhD (Management). Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, MALAYSIA

Copyright: © 2021 Ostapenko, R. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.